

ISW

In Silico World: Lowering barriers to ubiquitous adoption of In Silico Trials
Grant Agreement No. 101016503

D3.2 - Identification of best certification strategy for initial data collections

Deliverable information	
WP number and title	WP3 - D3.2 - Identification of best certification strategy for initial data collections
Lead beneficiary	UNICT
Dissemination level	Public
Due date	M18
Actual date of delivery	28/07/2022
Author	UNICT
Contributors	TUE, UNIBO, UVA, EMC

The following document reflects only the author's view. The Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016503

Quality assurance

To ensure the quality and correctness of this deliverable, we implied an internal review and validation process. The deliverable was drafted by partner UNICT. All partners contributed to and reviewed the overall draft. Finally, the semi-final version was submitted to internal reviewers, for a final review and validation.

Version	Date	Status	Author	
V 1.0	08/04/2022	Draft	UNICT	Creation of the document
V 2.0	27/06/2022	Intermediate Version	All partners involved	Update
	19/09/2022	Corrected version	TUe	Update
V 2.0	28/07/2022	Final version	UNICT	Finalization of the document

Table of contents

1. Introduction	3
1.1. Introduction to WP3 activities	3
1.2. Description of the content of this deliverable.....	3
2. General Overview.....	3
2.1. Description of the initial data collections	3
2.2. Identification of best certification strategy (general description of the strategy)	5
2.2.1. FFRValid certification strategy	6
2.2.2. HFValid certification strategy.....	7
2.2.3. TBValid certification strategy.....	7
2.2.4. StentValid certification strategy	7
2.3. Identification of methods to deal with data uncertainty and missing data in validation collections	7
3. Conclusion.....	8
4. References	8

1. Introduction

1.1. Introduction to WP3 activities

To put this deliverable in its context part of what was written in the proposal is depicted below as an introduction. In general, before an In Silico Trial solution can be used, it is necessary to demonstrate that its predictions are accurate in the intended context of use. Following the terminology introduced by the ASME VV40-2018, the ISW consortium will refer to this activity as *credibility assessment*. The goal of WP3 is to provide the experimental data required to assess the credibility of all solutions developed in WP2. More importantly, to address the lack of independent validation collections (barrier B2), the ISW consortium plans:

1. to curate and publish 7 validation collections, in order to facilitate and expedite the development (process) for/of other IST solutions;
2. to verify/ensure that the quality of the generated validation collections is sufficient to develop models.
3. to quantify precision and accuracy of the experimental methods used to generate the data, so to qualify their quality with respect to their use as validation collections;
4. to draft/define/indicate a set of specifications for any publicly available data collection to be used for the credibility assessment;
5. to curate and publish other data collections according to such specifications;
6. to develop/release tools that can be used to generate digital patients for future ISTs.

From M01, WP3 will work with partner TUE on the curation of data from the FAME-1 and FAME-3 studies (i.e., data from 1000 and 1500 patients randomly selected for Percutaneous Coronary Intervention (PCI) or Coronary Artery Bypass Graft (CABG) surgery) into a public collection suitable to validate any in silico trials solutions aimed to predict angio- based fractional flow reserve (FFR), and other in silico biomarkers for treatment stratification of coronary stenosis (FFRValid collection). Initially, the focus will be on the curation aspects and data certification, with specific reference to supporting regulatory accreditation. At M09, we submitted the first draft regarding data curation (D3.1). This will be used to create two additional public validation collections from the data used to validate the BoneStrength and UISS-TB solutions, namely HFValid and TBValid. This is the second draft of the guideline on curation and data certification planned to be delivered by M18 (D3.2). From M25 to M36, TUE will work on the publication of the clinical data collection used to validate (1) UISS-MS with UNICT, (2) AngioSupport with partners UvA and EMC, and (3) ForceLoss with UNIBO. In parallel, starting from M13, TUE will work on a horizontal task on more advanced aspects of validation data management: data assimilation, handling missing data, and the creation of synthetic data collections.

NOTE: It has been decided that the ISR3D model activities will be taken over as far as possible by AngioSupport. An addition to AngioSupport will be made to still use StentValid as one of the data collections.

1.2. Description of the content of this deliverable

The purpose of this deliverable is to identify, if possible, a general certification strategy that could be effective for all validation data collections. In section 2.1 a description of the initial data collections is given (partly taken for the proposal) and a proposal for the certification strategy is described. In section 2.2 general remarks relevant for data collection certification are made and in the subsequent subsections these are further specified for the different data collections considered. In section 2.3 a short remark is made on the methods to deal with data uncertainty and missing data in validation collections and put in context of our general strategy.

2. General Overview

2.1. Description of the initial data collections

Synthetic data collections, a concept originally developed in demographic sciences, are collections of artificially generated data that manifest all statistical properties of the collection of observational data they

mimic, which cannot be made publicly available due to the presence of sensitive information. The same technique can also be used to do/perform a cohort expansion, e.g., the creation of a large synthetic cohort (data collection) from observations on a small/limited/minimal number/set of (real) patients.

The validation collections of the ISW consortium are the following:

1. **FFRValid:** in collaboration with the Catharina hospital in Eindhoven, the angio-based data that has been gathered in the FAME 1 and FAME 3 clinical trials to validate FFR guided versus angio-based PCI and FFR guided PCI versus CABG respectively. The data collections consist of 1000 and 1500 X-ray angio's, partly mono-plane and partly biplane, combined with locally measured and pull-back FFR at specific annotated branches of the coronary tree. Automated segmentation will be developed and carried out to represent each patient's coronary arteries in terms of centrelines and local diameter. Patient phenotype and all available and relevant patient record data will be collected in a predefined database structure. Data uncertainty will be defined based on known or estimated accuracy measures. The resulting data collection will be suitable for validation of angio-based computed (virtual) FFR procedures that can be used in ISTs for medical devices such as stents, hypothermia procedures, and decision support systems for PCI planning. The data collection will also be used to develop procedures for data assimilation, generation of virtual patient cohorts, sensitivity analysis and uncertainty quantification, hybrid modelling combining data driven models with mechanistic models and meta-modelling. We will use AngioSupport to evaluate the data collection certification.
2. **HFValid:** through its linked third party Istituto Ortopedico Rizzoli (IOR), UNIBO has access to over 4000 CT scans of the thigh region, originally collected to enable CT-based surgical planning of a total hip replacement procedure, under an informed consent that included also secondary use for research. The IOR local ethical committee allowed UNIBO to publicly share around 5% of the collected CT scans upon irreversible anonymization. The BoneStrength solution requires CT images to be densitometrically calibrated, segmented, meshed with parabolic tetrahedra, and then projected back onto the calibrated CT data, to generate a heterogeneous finite element model of the patient's femur. Therefore, the HFValid collection will also include calibration CT scans (with phantom), anthropometric and clinical patient information (i.e., height, weight, and fracture status after 5 years) that are needed to generate the (bone) model. In addition, UNIBO is also exploring the generation of synthetic data collections, specifically toward the generation of virtual cohorts for phase III In Silico Trials (with over 1000 virtual patients).
3. **TBValid:** TBValid is a collection of immunological data coming from healthy volunteers and patients with active tuberculosis treated with Archivel RUTI therapeutic vaccine in a phase II interventional randomized clinical trial. Partner UNICT has access to this collection under the EC funded STriTuVaD project but cannot share it before the end of the project. To overcome this issue, partner UNICT produced derivative, synthetic data applying the procedure described in [1]. The expected quality of the (synthetic) data is guaranteed by the procedures described in the clinical trial dossier, which does not affect data quality. Clean File for the final database will be declared when all data have been entered and a quality check on a sample of the data has been performed. The database will be locked after Clean File has been declared and data extracted for statistical analysis.
4. **MSValid:** through its third-party Multiple Sclerosis Center (Neurology Unit, Garibaldi Hospital, Catania, Italy) UNICT is going to have access to data collected on a minimum of 150 adults affected by the two most common form of multiple sclerosis (MS), i.e., primary progressing relapsing-remitting MS and secondary progressing MS. For each patient, the following information will be collected: age at MS onset, baseline MRI lesion load, oligoclonal bands status and the administered treatment. These features are widely accepted as prognostic parameters of MS. Expected quality of the data will be guaranteed by the procedures followed by the Hospital data center. In particular, demographic and clinical data are collected by medical personnel experienced in the management of MS patients and with certification of ability to perform the Neurostatus; MRIs are acquired according to the protocols

described in the international guidelines for MS and by neuroradiologists with experience in the field; examination of the cerebrospinal fluid is conducted by an internal laboratory that annually participates in quality checks by the Italian Association of Neuroimmunology.

5. **DPValid:** for this validation collection, UNIBO is using data collected at its linked third party Istituto Ortopedico Rizzoli, as part of a separately funded and ongoing project. This study is recruiting at least 10 adult healthy volunteers and at least 10 elderly patients with dynapenia (loss of muscle force). For each subject an MRI of the lower body, an isokinetic dynamometry of leg extension, a maximal isometric dynamometry of leg extension, and multi-channel electromyography of the most relevant muscles of the thigh will be collected, under an informed consent that explicitly authorizes the sharing of these data in anonymized form for research purposes.
6. **ValveValid:** a total number of 600 Computed Tomography Angiographies (CTA's) of patients that received an aortic valve replacement via a TAVI procedure have been made available as a validation collection for TAVI procedures but will also be used to design and execute an IST in which two different valve designs (Medtronic/Edwards) will be compared with respect to the need of pacing the heart. The outcome of the IST can be compared with real clinical data that show a significant difference between the two brands. Software tools to derive a synthetic (virtual) validated patient cohort will be tested and results will be published and made available to the community. Within scope of the ISW project, we will analyze the useful parts of the data collection and assess which accuracy metric suits the data collection (see WP3). All data to be used for ValveValid were collected in a clinical study conducted by the same team involved in the FAME 1 and FAME 3 studies (see FFRValid description). Therefore, the same or similar data quality (and level of accuracy) is to be expected. However, whether such data quality level is representative of other clinical centres is not known and should be investigated in a separate study.
7. **StentValid:** a data collection of 846 angio-based coronary artery datasets (DICOM x-ray data, bi-plane but also mono-plane) will be made available as a validation collection for the evaluation of PCI procedures with different stent types. Another data collection of 1500 angio-based coronary artery datasets (similar to the datasets above) will be made available as a validation collection for the evaluation of PCI procedures with different stent types. The Mechanistic model for this data collection intends to simulate the outcome of a study in which 1500 patients were randomized and treated with two drug eluting stent types, one biodegradable (Optimax) and one coated (Abbott). These data collections will be used to validate activities in the AngioSupport solution of WP2. The StentValid cohort from the EMC for the validation of AngioSupport will be mainly based on the large database of the biodegradable stent studies (Absorb/Abbot) organized and executed by and within EMC.

2.2. Identification of best certification strategy (general description of the strategy)

Errors in measuring quantitative data can be an important source of bias in experimental studies. Measurement bias refers to any systematic, non-random and random error that occurs in the collection of data in a study. The choice of the instrument and its inner uncertainty may influence the quality of the model prediction, therefore, in conducting studies, it is important to assess the quality of measurements.

Apart from measurement uncertainty, assessing the accuracy of predictive models is critical because predictive models have been increasingly used across various disciplines and predictive accuracy determines the quality of resultant predictions. Accuracy of the predictive models is critical as it determines the quality of their predictions that form the scientific evidence for decision-making and policy. Therefore, it is important to correctly assess the predictive accuracy of a model.

A potential approach to identify the best certification strategy for in silico models reads as follows:

- For each measurable variable, one can identify the information about its precision and its reproducibility, which means:
 - Estimating the degree of accuracy of the tool/instrument used to measure each entity

- Estimating the distance between the measured and the predicted quantity (for example in terms of the number of “transformations” required to move from the experimental to the in silico variable) when the measured variable does not correspond to the in silico one.
- Estimate the error that results from the circumstances in which the measurements have been performed.
- Evaluating the sparseness of the measure, identified as the spatio-temporal density of the information. Sparse data is a variable in which the cells of the matrix do not contain actual data within data analysis. Sparse data is empty or has a zero value. Sparse data is different from missing data because sparse data show up as empty or zero while missing data do not show what some or any of the values are. When sparse data are present in datasets, they create dense data. There are two types of sparsity:
 - Controlled sparsity happens when there is a range of values for multiple dimensions that have no value
 - Random sparsity occurs when there is sparse data scattered randomly throughout the datasets
- Inhomogeneity of data due to different measurement protocols that are used (e.g., in a multi centre trial). A strategy to express this in accuracy and/or sparseness needs to be developed.

So most of the time, one comes across sparse data (in other words, data collections with missing records). One may use random imputation algorithms but it affects the model. The strategy developed for this is to deal with this issue by using deep generative models (AI model) to impute the values, thereby reducing the uncertainty of the mechanistic model as much as possible. The AI models will be evaluated by testing out how precisely it can estimate if some values are deleted on purpose (where the ground truth value is known).

Data certification according to the strategy depicted above is needed to prove that data is suitable for performing an in silico trial. This trial makes use of one or more mechanistic models (WP2) which means that we can only certify data as suitable if the model that is used produces clinically relevant and sufficiently accurate model output. In other cases, the data should be quantified as unsuitable. The modelers (WP2) should perform a VVUQ (parameter identifiability, sensitivity analysis) to make this certification possible. In addition, if synthetic data sets are produced the model outcome can/will be used to filter out relevant and, if needed, specific data sets.

So data certification can't be independent of the in silico models that use these data and strong collaboration with WP2 is indispensable. In the implementation and demonstration phases of WP3 (tasks 3.3 and 3.4) this collaboration will be intensified.

2.2.1. FFRValid certification strategy

It is necessary to know the technical requirements necessary for the data set by first performing VVUQ onto the AngioSupport model. Verification has already been done since the AngioSupport model's performance has been benchmarked against other studies. Uncertainty quantification will be performed to evaluate the error within the model output. In order to reduce this error, a sensitivity analysis will be performed to evaluate the model's most important parameters that have the greatest contribution to the variance of the fractional flow reserve. The most important parameters will be assessed accurately through other simulations and measurements. Finally, validation will be done by comparing the results to the original clinical data of the FAME studies. The predicted fractional flow reserves will be compared to their respective ground truths by using the FAME1 and FAME3 study datasets, which also contain an extensive follow-up study allowing for the validation of the model's long-term predictions, such as mortality rates and various morbidities that can come up.

Once the necessary input ranges are known, we can assess whether our synthetically generated data is in accordance with the necessary input of our model. Filters will be used to exclude unphysiologically generated angiograms based both on geometric parameters and model outcomes. The degree of accuracy and corresponding uncertainty of the measured data will be assessed based on the technical documentation of the measurement device, sparseness, and inhomogeneity. TBased on this, the degree of accuracy of the simulation outcomes will be assessed.

2.2.2. HFValid certification strategy

The accuracy of the clinical CT scans used in the HFValid collection can be extracted from technical data sheets and periodic machine calibrations. We plan to explore phantomless calibration to reduce effects of possible variations in CT scan X-ray source and detector performances over time.

Technical validation of the employed finite-element modelling technique was already conducted on cadaveric femurs. Extensive VV&UQ activities are being performed on the mechanistic model in order to identify the most influent parameters for the output.

2.2.3. TBValid certification strategy

The degree of accuracy of measured data will be gathered from the technical documentation of the tool/instrument used (for example, from the Technical Data Sheet, sample manual). The estimation of the distance between the measured and the predicted quantity will be assessed by taking into account the transformations needed to derive interleukins quantity from the number of cells that actually secrete them. For the other entities (i.e., cellular entities, age, vitamin D quantities, BMI) no transformations are required as they are measured in the same way UISS-TB M&S platform does. The degree of the sparseness of the measures will be computed evaluating the difference between the expected timing of the measure against the actual one. Random sparsity in this case is not present as the measures are reported in regular intervals.

2.2.4. StentValid certification strategy

The StentValid data collection will be certified in a similar way as the FFRValid dataset. In this case the outcome of the follow-up studies regarding patency of the deployed/placed stents will be compared to the model predictions. The uncertainty in the data collection will be evaluated by its ability to give model output that can be compared with follow-up data using AngioSupport. In this sense, since no separate model verification has been performed, it is also providing first model verification data.

2.3. Identification of methods to deal with data uncertainty and missing data in validation collections

To manage the incompleteness of data collection, we have designed the pipelines with Deep Generative Models (DGMs). In the implementation phase of WP3 details of these pipelines will be described and evaluated such that scientific publications can be made. These models will be capable of generating synthetic data with corresponding patient characteristics which help to deal with patient privacy intervention as well. The Generative Adversarial Network (GANs) architecture for HFValid data collection to produce hip fracture CT scans with patient height and weight have been designed and needs further evaluation and optimisation. Also a design of the Variational Autoencoder (VAE) architecture for coronary artery geometry generation with corresponding age and gender information for patient-specific analyses has been established. This method aims to represent the FFRValid data collection. Similarly, we are also working on TBValid and StentValid data collections.

In order to deal with data uncertainty, the synthetic data and the methods developed for uncertainty quantification of the synthetic data based on the mechanistic models provided by WP2 still have to be validated.

3. Conclusion

Although the development and implementation of the technical certification tools are ongoing and part of D3.3 (M36), the strategy that will followed for the different data collections has been defined. Public release of the data collections was planned at this stage. However, due to the recent changes in the privacy policies at almost all clinical sites, the legal certification (final step) has not been taken yet. Eventually, the generation of synthetic datasets will solve this problem, but the implementation is still ongoing and planned for M36 (D3.3).

4. References

- [1] M. A. Juárez *et al.*, “Generation of digital patients for the simulation of tuberculosis with UISS-TB,” *BMC Bioinformatics*, vol. 21, no. S17, p. 449, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.1186/s12859-020-03776-z.